

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Title: An adaptive search algorithm for multiplicity dynamic flexible job shop scheduling with new order arrival

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1. Example description

Table 1 provides an example of MDFJSP with two new orders and three machines. Initially (order1), each job type has a certain number of available positions. The dynamic scheduling system then implements the schedule until the next order arrives. The process of dynamic scheduling is repeated until all jobs have been completed. The example is used to illustrate the MDFJSP in Figure 1.

Table 1. A MDFJSP example with 2 new orders and 3 machines.

N_{1r}	N_{2r}	r	j	M1	M2	M3
3	2	1	1	29	11	28
			2	14	15	24
			3	18	25	25
3	2	2	1	12	16	25
			2	22	15	14
			3	26	26	20

Fig. 1. An example of MDFJSP with the arrival of the new order.

Figure 1-a demonstrates that two task kinds, $r=1,2$, are processed on three machines $m=1,2,3$. In addition, six jobs 11,12,13;21,22,23 in order one must be planned, and order two includes four new jobs 14,15;24,25 that come at time 50. First, we establish the scheduling scheme based on the first order, as depicted in Fig. 2. (a). At time 50, ongoing activities 222,122,113 are not halted, but the rescheduling procedure is initiated when order number two arrives. All non-processed operations are rescheduled according to the proposed DA3C once a rescheduling process begins. Consequently, 19 operations must be scheduled for time 50. (reschedule point). Figure 1 depicts the new schedule scheme acquired after the arrival of the second order (b).

2. Parameter settings for instances

MDFJSP instances generated as per real-world problems and generation values are shown in Table 2. In Table 2, 'randi' denotes the uniform distribution of integer numbers.

Table 2. Parameter settings for instances

Parameter	Value
Total number of machines (M)	randi[10,20]
Total number of job types (R)	randi[5,10]
Total number of operations of job type r (J_r)	randi[5,10]
Number of available machines per operation	randi[1, M]
Processing time of an operation (t_{rjm})	randi[1,20]
Total number of new orders (S)	randi[1,5]
Total number of job type r in new order s (N_{sr})	randi[10,20]
Mean interarrival time of new jobs (λ)	randi[200,800]

3. Parameter settings

Parameter selection plays a crucial role in algorithm performance. Three parameters can affect the efficiency of the proposed algorithm. In this section, we calibrate the algorithm parameters with the Taguchi method of design of experiment (DOE) (Mandavi, Shiri, and Rahnamayan 2015). The DOE is an effective and efficient investigative method widely used to evaluate the effect of multiple factors on different algorithms. The three parameters $\{D, iter_{stop}, b\}$ define the FRAS. D is the number of generated initial feasible solutions with fluid construction heuristic method (FCH) for each iteration of FRAS, $iter_{stop}$ is the permitted maximum iteration number with no improvement of ITS, and b is the alfa parameter which used to balance the stochasticity and covetousness of the proposed algorithm. Ten randomly generated instances are selected to identify the effect of the three parameters. The parameter D has four possible values: $\{10, 20, 40, 80\}$, the parameter $iter_{stop}$ can be $\{10, 20, 30, 40\}$, and the parameter b can be $\{0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4\}$. As shown in Table 3, the parameter combinations are represented with the orthogonal array L_{16} . The average makespans (C_{avg}) of ten instances, obtained through 30 independent runs of the FRAS, are used as the response values in our analysis. Factor level trend can be seen from Fig. 4. It can be seen from the Fig. 2 that FRAS with control parameters of $iter_{stop} = 40$, $D = 40$, and $b = 0.3$, perform better.

Table 3. Orthogonal array and average response values.

Combinations	Parameters			C_{avg}
	$iter_{stop}$	D	b	
1	10	10	0.1	2010
2	10	20	0.2	2030.7
3	10	40	0.3	2017.7
4	10	80	0.4	2014
5	20	10	0.2	2025
6	20	20	0.1	2034
7	20	40	0.4	2016.7
8	20	80	0.3	2025.3
9	30	10	0.3	2032.3
10	30	20	0.4	2035.3
11	30	40	0.1	2021
12	30	80	0.2	2017.3
13	40	10	0.4	2024.7
14	40	20	0.3	2000.7
15	40	40	0.2	2006.3
16	40	80	0.1	2024.3

Fig. 2. The trend of the factor level.

4. Comparison with optimal value

This section tests FRAS on multiplicity instances (data01~data08) to compare with optimal value. The optimal values are obtained with KNITRO 9.0.1 solver. Table 4 shows the optimal value obtain with respect to time. The KNITRO 9.0.1 solver can only optimally solve the instance with equal or less than $\{N = 9, M = 10\}$ within the limit of two hours of computation time. The best-obtained solution by FRAS in data6~data7 outperforms the KNITRO with a high gap. However, the exact method is not effective for solving problems with a larger number of jobs and machines.

Table 4. Computation results on generated instances.

Instance	$N \times M$	KNITRO 9.0.1			FRAS	
		C_{max}	$t(s)$	Optimality Gap (%)	Best(avg)	$t(s)$
data01	3×3	303	0.34	0	303(303)	0.70
data02	6×3	551	0.48	0	551(553)	1.05
data03	6×5	370	0.59	0	370(371)	0.85
data04	9×5	555	0.72	0	555(557)	1.19
data05	9×10	272	46.76	0	272(272.8)	20.06
data06	15×10	583	7200	19.68	394(396.2)	12.26
data07	20×10	1574	7200	99.23	770(772.5)	22.88
data08	40×10	—	—	—	1457(1462.7)	40.10

5. Statistical analysis

In this section, the Wilcoxon test is used to compare the FRAS with reference algorithms to check whether the proposed algorithm outperforms all reference algorithms statistically. The Wilcoxon is a non-parametric test method that is suitable for continuous optimization problems in multiple-problem analysis (García et al. 2008). Table 5 summarizes the results of applying the Wilcoxon test on average makespan. They display the sum of rankings obtained in each comparison and the the $p - value$ associated. The FRAS outperforms these reference algorithms considering independent pairwise comparisons due to the $p - value$ are below $\alpha = 0.05$. However, Wilcoxon's test performs individual comparisons between two algorithms. If we include them within the multiple comparisons, the $p - value$ obtained is $p = 0.0155$. Then, it can be deduced that HFMAE outperforms the three reference algorithms in terms of solution quality with a level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$.

Table 5. Wilcoxon test considering average makespan.

FRAS vs.	R^+	R^-	$p - value$
SLGA	36	0	0.00390625
2SGA	36	0	0.00390625
GRAS	36	0	0.00390625

6. Sensitivity analysis

To further assess the extent of our proposed algorithm, an instance with $\{M = 10, S = 5, R = 20\}$ is used to perform sensitivity analysis to analyze the impact of the time interval between new orders' arrival on the objective and the mean total response time (TR). Fig. 3 shows the results of the sensitivity analysis.

Fig. 3. The impact of the time interval between new orders' arrival on the objective and the mean total response time (TR).

From Fig. 3, it can be observed that increasing the time interval between new orders' arrival leads to an increase in makespan and a decrease in the mean total response time. This can be explained by the fact that fewer jobs need to be rescheduled at each rescheduling point, reducing the complexity of the scheduling problem. As a result, FRAS can converge to a final solution more quickly. Additionally, a more significant time interval between new orders' arrival makes the scheduling system more myopic, limiting the potential for finding better overall schedules. These findings indicate that FRAS effectively captures the impact of the time interval between new orders' arrival on system performance. Furthermore, the proposed algorithm demonstrates good stability and robustness across various levels of new orders' arrival time intervals.

7. Process information and production data

Table 6. The processing information of the three types of parts.

Part types	Operation	Processing time
r	j	(r, j, m, t_{rjm})
1	1	(1,1,1,18)
	2	(1,2,3,10)
	3	(1,3,1,21)
	4	(1,4,6,19)
	5	(1,5,7,28) (1,5,8,28) (1,5,9,28)
	6	(1,6,11,10)
	7	(1,7,13,20) (1,7,14,20)
	8	(1,8,15,32) (1,8,16,32) (1,8,17,32)
	9	(1,9,18,19) (1,9,19,19) (1,9,20,19)
	10	(1,10,10,8)
2	1	(2,1,2,18)
	2	(2,2,3,10)
	3	(2,3,4,21)

	4	(2,4,5,19)
	5	(2,5,7,28) (2,5,8,28) (2,5,9,28)
	6	(2,6,11,10)
	7	(2,7,13,20) (2,7,14,20)
	8	(2,8,15,32) (2,8,16,32) (2,8,17,32)
	9	(2,9,18,19) (2,9,19,19) (2,9,20,19)
	10	(2,10,10,8)
	1	(3,1,2,23)
	2	(3,2,3,14)
	3	(3,3,4,25)
	4	(3,4,5,26) (3,4,6,26)
3	5	(3,5,7,42) (3,5,8,42) (3,5,9,42) (3,5,10,42)
	6	(3,6,11,15)
	7	(3,7,12,25)
	8	(3,8,13,31) (3,8,14,31)
	9	(3,9,15,48) (3,9,16,48) (3,9,17,48)
	10	(3,10,18,28) (3,10,19,28)
	11	(3,11,7,10) (3,11,8,10) (3,11,9,10) (3,11,10,10)

Table 7. The detailed information of the five cases.

Cases	Orders (s)	Order arrival time (A_s)	Number of each type of part contained in each order		
			r_1	r_2	r_3
Data01	1-1	0	22	13	16
	1-2	537	19	17	29
Data02	2-1	0	11	14	15
	2-2	641	22	20	29
	2-3	2537	12	16	11
Data03	3-1	0	11	15	26
	3-2	1075	19	18	15
	3-3	1652	15	21	18
	3-4	4247	24	12	25
Data04	4-1	0	18	16	28
	4-2	2253	29	16	15
	4-3	2885	19	19	28
	4-4	4726	25	24	20
	4-5	4937	11	12	11
Data05	5-1	0	24	13	12
	5-2	1161	29	24	11
	5-3	3214	22	13	24
	5-4	3327	20	26	23
	5-5	3437	29	20	28

References

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